

Supplemental Table 1. Equations for corrected milk and for energy in milk in their original format.

Approach ¹	Equation ^{2,3}	Citation; Notes ^{3,4}
Gaines		
Gross energy, kcal/lb milk	132.06 x lb M + 4964 x lb F	Gaines and Davidson, 1923
4% fat-corrected milk, kg	0.4 x kg M + 15 x kg F	330.62 kcal/lb divisor
Tyrrell and Reid		
Gross energy, kcal/lb milk		Tyrrell and Reid, 1965
Eqn. 1	41.63 x F% + 24.13 x CP % + 21.60 x L% - 11.72	SEM = 3.8, CV = 1.22%
Eqn. 2	40.72 x F% + 22.65 x CP% + 102.77	SEM = 7.2, CV = 2.31%
Eqn. 4	44.01 x F% + 163.56	SEM = 9.6, CV = 3.06%
Eqn. 6	41.84 x F% + 22.29 x SNF% -25.58	SEM = 4.0, CV = 1.27%
Solids-corrected milk, kg	12.3 x kg F + 6.56 x kg SNF - 0.0752 x kg M	340 kcal/lb divisor = 1 lb 4% fat milk from Gaines (1928)
3.5% FPCM corrected milk		
Eqn. A.	0.323 x kg M + 12.82 x kg F + 7.13 x kg CP	317.77 kcal/lb divisor, 3.5% F, 3.2% CP
Eqn. B1.	0.327 x kg M + 12.95 x kg F + 7.20 x kg CP	DRMS, 2014; 314 kcal/lb divisor; 3.5% F, 3.2% CP
Eqn. B2	0.327 x kg M + 12.95 x kg F + 7.65 x kg TP	DRMS, 2014; 314 kcal/lb divisor; 1.063 multiplier to convert CP to TP
Perrin		
kcal/100 g milk	9.11 x F% + 37.4 x (Total Nitrogen% - Nonprotein Nitrogen%) + 3.95 x L%	Perrin, 1958 37.4 = 6.38 conversion factor for milk N x 5.86 kcal/g milk CP
Sjaunja		
Gross energy, kJ/kg milk		Sjaunja et al., 1990a,b L = anhydrous lactose CV = 0.56%
Eqn 1.	38.30 x F g/kg + 24.20 x CP g/kg + 16.54 x L g/kg + 20.7	
Eqn. 2	38.10 x F g/kg + 21.48 x CP g/kg + 896.0	CV = 0.82%
Eqn. 3	43.92 x F g/kg + 1393.4	CV = 1.81%
Eqn. 4	38.30 x F g/kg + 24.20 x CP g/kg + 783.2	CV = 0.89%
Energy-corrected milk, kg	0.01 x kg M + 12.2 x kg F + 7.7 x kg CP + 5.3 x kg L	Energy equation divisor: 3,140 kJ/kg Milk ~ 750 kcal/kg ~ energy in 1 kg 4% fat milk
	0.25 x kg M + 12.2 x kg F + 7.7 x kg CP	
IFCN		
Energy corrected milk, kg	(kg M x (0.383 x F% + 0.242 x CP% + 0.7832) / 3.1138)	Reincke et al., 2018 4% fat, 3.3% protein basis
Divided by 3.1138	0.252 x kg M + 12.30 x kg F + 7.77 x kg CP	
NASEM		
Milk NEL, Mcal/kg Milk		NASEM, 2021 L = 0.0485 kg/kg M if unknown. CP basis
Eqn. 3-14a	9.29 x kg F/kg M + 5.5 x kg CP/kg M + 3.95 x kg L/kg M	
Eqn. 3-14b	9.29 x kg F/kg M + 5.85 x kg TP/kg Milk + 3.95 x kg L/kg M	TP basis
Eqn. 3-14c	0.360 + 0.0969 x F%	Use if only fat is measured.

¹ Eqn. = equation.

² lb = pounds; Energy equations are given in the units of the original work.

³ CP = milk crude protein as N x 6.38; F = milk fat; L = lactose; M = milk; TP = milk true protein.

⁴ CV = coefficient of variation, SEM = standard error of the mean

NOTES

The form of lactose used varies among equations. Lactose is calculated by difference from 100 minus fat, protein, and ash in Tyrrell and Reid (1965) and is anhydrous lactose in Perrin (1958), Sjaunja et al. (1990a,b) and NASEM (2021).

REFERENCES

DRMS (Dairy Record Management Services). 2014. DHI glossary. Accessed online March 26, 2022. <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.686.2482&rep=rep1&type=pdf>

Gaines, W.L. 1928. The energy basis of measuring milk yield in dairy cows. Univ. of Illinois Agr. Expt. Sta., Bull. 308. Urbana, IL.
<https://www.ideals.illinois.edu/bitstream/handle/2142/3126/energybasisofmea00gain.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

Gaines, W.L. and F.A. Davidson. 1923. Relation between percentage fat content and yield of milk. Correction of milk yield for fat content. Agr. Expt. Sta., Bull. 245. Urbana, IL.
<https://www.ideals.illinois.edu/bitstream/handle/2142/3304/relationbetweenp00gain.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

NASEM (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine). 2021. Nutrient requirements of dairy cattle, 8th rev. ed. The National Academies Press, Washington, DC.
doi.org/10.17226/25806

Perrin, D.R. 1958. 709. The calorific value of milk of different species. J. Dairy Res. 25:215-220.
doi.org/10.1017/S0022029900009213

Reincke, K., A. Saha, and L. Wyrzykowski. 2018. The global dairy world 2017/2018. Results of the IFCN dairy report 2018. IFCN Dairy Research Network, Kiel, Germany. Oct., 8, 2018. Accessed online March 26, 2022. <https://ifcndairy.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/Dairy-Report-Article-2018.pdf>

Sjaunja, L.O., L. Baevre, L. Junkkarinen, J. Pedersen, and J. Setälä. 1990a. Measurement of the total energy content of cow's milk and the energy value of milk fat and milk protein. In Proc 27th Biennial Session of Intl. Comm. For Anim. Recording (ICAR), Paris, France, July 2-6, 1990. Pp 152-155. doi.org/10.3920/978-90-8686-500-0

Sjaunja, L.O., L. Baevre, L. Junkkarinen, J. Pedersen, and J. Setälä. 1990b. A Nordic proposal for an energy corrected milk (ECM) formula. In Proc 27th Biennial Session of Intl. Comm. For Anim. Recording (ICAR), Paris, France, July 2-6, 1990. pp 156-157.

Tyrrell, H.F., and J.T. Reid. 1965. Prediction of the energy value of cow's milk. *J. Dairy Sci.* 48:1215-1223. doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(65)88430-2